

ADAPTIVE TRAFFIC SIGNAL CONTROL USING AI AND DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS FOR SMART URBAN MOBILITY

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ABSTRACT

Urban traffic jams remain a pressing issue due to increasing vehicle concentrations, inadaptive traffic signal management, and unreliable road conditions. Fixed or semi-adaptive traditional traffic control systems cannot adaptively change in real-time traffic environments, leading to wasted time, excessive fuel usage, and greater pollutant emissions.

This study proposes a comprehensive framework for the optimization of urban traffic, leveraging predictive modeling, adaptive signal control, and distributed messaging infrastructure. The platform collects real-time sensor information, employs machine learning techniques for short-term traffic prediction, and optimizes signal timing through heuristic approaches such as Simulated Annealing (SA) and Reinforcement Learning (RL). The asynchronous messaging architecture supports flexible communication among prediction modules, controllers, and external services to facilitate flexibility and scalability.

Experimental validation was conducted using the SUMO traffic simulator, where a standard fixed-cycle signal scheme was compared to the proposed adaptive scheme. Results indicate that there is a 21.6% reduction in average waiting time, a 12.9% reduction in CO₂ emissions, and a 15.6% improvement in fuel efficiency. These findings validate the effectiveness of the system in mitigating congestion and enabling green urban mobility.

Future work will involve incorporating vehicle-to-everything communication data (V2X communication), multi-intersection coordination, and deep learning traffic flow predictions in order to better enhance adaptability and robustness at the large-scale deployment stage.

Keywords: *Intelligent Transportation Systems, Traffic Optimization, Adaptive Signal Control, Predictive Modeling, Reinforcement Learning, Smart Cities*

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing problem of traffic congestion in urban centers has become the trademark of modern cities, with far-reaching effects on economic efficacy, environmental sustainability, and the overall health of urban dwellers. With expanding urban populations and the unabating use of private cars, the volume of traffic on roads tends to outstrip the planned capacity of the available network, particularly in populous metropolitan cities [1]. This imbalance between traffic demand and supply of infrastructure is felt as persistent congestion, leading to highly increased travel times, wasted fuel, and excessive levels of harmful air emissions and greenhouse gases. These impacts extend beyond individual annoyance, affecting supply chains,

limiting economic activity, and encouraging climate change [2].

The traditional method of traffic management, based heavily on fixed signal control systems, is growing ever more insufficient to respond to the dynamic and often unpredictable nature of traffic in the 21st century. While relatively easy to implement, these static signal timings inherently lack the capacity to adjust in real-time to the constantly changing traffic demands, unexpected events like accidents or road closures, and inclement weather conditions that can have a profound impact on traffic flow [3]. The inflexibility of fixed-time control systems tends to create non-optimal signal settings, which ironically produce congestion, leading to excessive queue formation, increased delays, and an elevated risk of stop-and-go traffic conditions, further contributing to increased fuel consumption

and emissions [4].

Realizing the limitations of the conventional approaches, Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) has been one of the leading research and development areas. ITS has the purpose of applying advanced technologies such as sensors, communication networks, data analysis, and intelligent computation to develop efficient, adaptive, and responsive traffic management [5]. Designing and deploying Adaptive Traffic Signal Control (ATSC) systems has been one of the major interests of ITS. In contrast to fixed-time schedules, ATSC schedules vary the timing of traffic lights according to prevailing traffic conditions. It has the purpose of enhancing the movement of traffic, minimizing the delay of the vehicles, and reducing the adverse environmental impact due to congestion [6].

New research within ATSC has been charting many new paths. Predictive modeling with the help of machine learning and statistics is gaining more and more influence. Predictive models are making short-term traffic volume predictions based on historic traffic, sensor measurements in real-time and external factors like weather and events. Accurate traffic prediction is crucial for intelligent and effective signal optimization [7]. One of the most critical areas for improvement is in the use of Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms. RL has the potential to allow traffic signal controllers to learn to optimize traffic signaling through experimentation with different actions and error-based learning. It can learn through interacting with the traffic environment and adapt in real-time without the need for complicated, pre-defined traffic models [8]. Also with the advent of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) come new possibilities. CAVs with their vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) and vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) capabilities have the potential to provide very detailed and timely information about vehicle positions, velocities, and planned itineraries. This copious information stream can be leveraged for enhancing situational awareness and for making more accurate and responsive traffic control strategies [9]. Multi-agent systems are also highly beneficial for traffic management [10].

Despite the huge potential and benefits brought with such recent approaches, there are many core issues that prevent ATSC systems from being implemented efficiently and on large scale. Scalability is the major issue. The majority of solutions, particularly those developed around

complex optimization algorithms, are heavy in computation and cannot scale economically to large and complex urban transportation networks. Real-time traffic management for the whole city requires computationally efficient algorithms along with distributed computing infrastructure that can efficiently handle the huge amount of data generated [11]. The quality and availability of real-time traffic data are also important limiting factors. Data-hungry approaches, such as predictive modeling and RL, are heavily dependent on accurate, complete, and timely data. Incomplete, noisy, or tardy data can severely undermine the performance and reliability of such systems. Interoperability and system integration represent further challenges. Seamless integration of disparate components, like sensors, controllers, communication networks, and data processing platforms, that are typically acquired from a variety of vendors, into a complete and functional system remains an elusive goal. Standard communication protocols and open, modular system architectures are necessary to achieve interoperability. Finally, ATSC systems must be robust and fault-tolerant to unexpected situations, sensor malfunctions, and communication disruptions. Fault-tolerant architectures, adaptive control techniques, and robust information handling methods are necessary to ensure reliable performance in the presence of uncertainty.

This work meets these challenges by introducing an integrated urban traffic optimization strategy. The approach combines synergistically short-term traffic flow forecasting, adaptive signal control, and distributed communication supported by a message-oriented middleware (MOM). This framework is such that it maximizes the strength of each module while minimizing its limitations. It gathers real-time data via a network of sensors, applies machine learning techniques to predict near-future traffic conditions, applies a metaheuristic optimization algorithm (Simulated Annealing) to determine the optimal signal durations, and applies a messaging infrastructure (specifically, infrastructures like MQTT or Kafka) to enable flexible, scalable, and fault-resilient communication between the various system components. This modular and integrated approach aims to achieve a much better efficiency of traffic flow, reduced levels of congestion, lower emissions of pollutants, and greater flexibility with the dynamic and usually uncertain nature of urban traffic conditions. The performance of the considered system is thoroughly tested with the aid of realistic simulation based on the SUMO

(Simulation of Urban Mobility) traffic simulator.

2. STATE OF THE ART

In the past, standard city traffic regulation has relied considerably on fixed-timing or, optimistically, semi-adaptive control schemes in plans. Such infrastructure operates at planned cycles that are typically fine-tuned to suit specific expected traffic conditions, for example, off-peak or peak-hour situations. Whilst easy to make use of, such an approach virtually lacks a level of sensitivity to effectively respond to real-city traffic's internal dynamism and stochasticity. Random events, such as accidents, roadworks, incidents, or even climatic changes, can cause traffic movements to change drastically, rendering pre-configured signal control settings highly inefficient and also contributing to more congestion, delays, and emissions [12]. This inherent limitation of traditional approaches has been the key reason for considerable research and development into more adaptive and dynamic traffic management strategies.

The domain of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) has seen substantial advancements in recent years, with special focus on adaptive traffic signal control (ATSC) system development and improvement. One of the leading research paths in ATSC is the use of reinforcement learning (RL). Compared to traditional control methods that rely on pre-established rules or fixed models, RL allows traffic signal controllers to learn the best control policies through real experience with the traffic environment. This is typically achieved by a trial-and-error procedure, wherein the controller (the "agent") takes actions (adjusting signal times), looks at the resulting state of the traffic network (e.g., delay, queue length), and receives a reward signal (e.g., penalty for increased congestion). Over time, the RL agent learns to connect actions with their consequences and finds a policy maximizing the sum of rewards, basically optimizing traffic flow [10], [13]. Recent advances in deep reinforcement learning (DRL), the marriage of RL and deep neural networks, have shown strong promise to handle the high-dimensional state and action spaces common to complex traffic networks. DRL allows the acquisition of complex, non-linear associations between traffic states and optimal control actions, which could be transformed into more effective and responsive signal control strategies. But the computational demands of DRL, particularly during

training, can be extremely high, which is a serious drawback for real-time application in dynamic, large-scale cityscapes. Also, explainability and trust issues arise with DRL, since the decision-making process of the neural network might be opaque, and it can be difficult for traffic engineers to understand and check the behavior of the system [14].

Along with the primary goal of minimizing car waiting times, there is growing realization of the need for multi-objective optimization in traffic light control. Modern urban traffic control is not only needed to look after efficiency but also eco-friendliness. Researchers are now working on how to minimize energy consumption, pollutant emissions, and noise pollution at the same time, in addition to the traditional methods like travel time and capacity [15]. This entails the fusion of different information sources, for example, traffic flow, vehicle emissions models, and even possibly air quality sensors. The control algorithms to be implemented will subsequently need to acquire solutions in satisfying these often competing requirements, making choices that are the best compromise between efficiency and ecological regard. Vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication is increasingly becoming a master enabler of this multi-objective optimization framework. V2I allows real-time sharing of vehicle-to-infrastructure information, such as detailed vehicle information about their locations, velocities, and even engine conditions. The rich information stream can be used to create more accurate and comprehensive traffic movement and emissions models, allowing for greater control of car trajectories and signal timings. Combined with the use of advanced optimization procedures and the incorporation of V2I data, traffic efficiency will be greatly improved along with improved environmental performance [16].

Predictive modeling is also included in modern ATSC systems. Predictive short-term traffic flow forecasting is crucial in enabling anticipatory as opposed to reactive control measures. With predictive traffic demand, signal times can be adjusted prior to congestion development and prior to the creation of unnecessary delays and even improving the performance of the network as a whole. Current research has focused on applying sophisticated machine learning techniques, namely deep learning models, to forecast traffic flows more accurately and robustly. Deep learning models can learn complex spatial and temporal interdependencies in traffic data, leveraging

historical traffic trends, real-time sensor readings, and environmental inputs such as weather, holidays, special events, and even social media metrics [17]. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), among other models, have been of particular interest due to their ability to represent road network connectivity in a good manner. GNNs are able to capture interactions among different road segments and intersections and the spreading of congestion within them, leading to higher accuracy of prediction, especially in complex urban scenarios [18]. With all these advanced models comes a greater computational complexity of the system.

Despite these significant advances, several key challenges continue to exist, which hinder the large-scale deployment and effectiveness of ATSC systems. Computational complexity of recent approaches, e.g., deep reinforcement learning approaches and complex deep learning prediction models, usually necessitates large computational resources, and therefore, their real-time application in high-dimensional dynamic urban environments is a highly challenging problem. This computational burden can limit the system's responsiveness and the agility of its response to changing traffic conditions. Additionally, the effectiveness of data-centric approaches, both predictive modeling and reinforcement learning, is directly coupled with data quality and availability. Delayed, noisy, or missing data can significantly deteriorate model accuracy and lead to sub-optimal control actions. Developing robust methodologies that are able to deal with data uncertainties and missing data is therefore a research priority [19]. Finally, the integration of a multitude of and often heterogeneous elements in a traffic management system poses a big challenge. Different sensors, controllers, communication networks, and data processing platforms, usually from different manufacturers, must be integrated together seamlessly to create a coherent and functioning system. Lack of interoperability between these constituents can rule out large-scale deployment, hinder full exploitation of existing resources, and introduce complexity in system maintenance and upgrading. Open architectures, standardized communication protocols, and modular system design are necessities to surmount this lack of interoperability [20]. Solving these issues of computational complexity, robustness and quality of data, and system integration holds the answer to unlocking the complete potential of intelligent, adaptive, and sustainable urban traffic management systems [20]. Solving these issues of computational

complexity, robustness and quality of data, and system integration is necessary in order to achieve the full potential of intelligent, adaptive, and sustainable urban traffic management systems.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study proposes an integrated approach to the optimization of urban traffic flow based on real-time data collection, short-term prediction of traffic flow, adaptive traffic signal control, and distributed communication through a message-oriented middleware. The overall system architecture, depicted in Figure 1, is meticulously designed to be modular, scalable, and adaptable, allowing for future extensions and modifications. The core principle is to dynamically adjust traffic signal timings at an intersection based on predicted traffic conditions, aiming to minimize average vehicle waiting times while adhering to operational and safety constraints.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Architecture Overview: This representation highlights the components and their interactions. Multiple urban intersections (I1, I2, I3) are equipped with sensors (S) and a local controller (C). Raw data (vehicle flow, densities, weather conditions) is transmitted via the messaging infrastructure (M) to the prediction server (P). The server returns optimized instructions to be applied at traffic lights, while third-party services (T) – such as fleet management systems – can subscribe to real-time information streams.

The foundation of the system is a heterogeneous sensor network, responsible for collecting real-time data about the traffic environment. This network, as illustrated in a typical intersection setup in Figure 2, comprises several key sensor types. Strategically positioned cameras, equipped with advanced computer vision algorithms, are used to detect the presence of vehicles, estimate traffic density, classify vehicle types (e.g., cars, trucks, buses), and identify incidents such as accidents or stalled

vehicles [21]. This visual data provides a rich and comprehensive understanding of the traffic situation at the intersection. Complementing the cameras are inductive loop detectors, embedded within the roadway surface. These loops measure vehicle counts and occupancy, providing believable and accurate data concerning traffic volume and flow rates [22]. Radar sensors are also part of the system to measure the speeds of vehicles so that traffic flow characteristics like average speed and headway can be estimated, which play an essential role in ascertaining the general state of traffic [23]. Furthermore, local meteorological stations monitor the environmental state in real time, i.e., temperature, precipitation (rain or snow), visibility, and wind speed. The weather state is observed to significantly affect the traffic dynamics and hence included into the forecasting models so as to advance their precision and strength [24]. The system is likewise extensible, with the potential for incorporating information from linked vehicles (V2X) in future forms, further expanding its situational awareness.

Fig 2. Detailed View Of A Connected Intersection.

The sensor network information is routed to a central prediction server, the analytical brain of the system. This server is responsible for making short-term traffic flow predictions, typically 5-10 minutes into the future, for each entrance to the intersection. The prediction process itself uses advanced machine learning techniques that can understand the complex and dynamic interrelation between historical traffic

patterns, current sensor readings, and contextual information. The prediction model takes a number of significant inputs: historical traffic flow, providing the baseline day-to-day and week-to-week fluctuation in traffic; current data from sensors built into cameras, inductive loops, and radars showing the state at the moment; and context, including weather forecast, news on any special event (such as concerts or sports events) expected to lead to a disruption, and any planned or unplanned roadworks closure. The model used would be a combination of deep learning that is either LSTM or GNN [25]. This combination is particularly well-suited for capturing both the temporal dependencies in traffic flow (using LSTM) and the spatial relationships between different road segments (using GNN). The predicted traffic flows, denoted as $\lambda_i(t)$ for approach i at time t , are a critical output of this stage and serve as a key input to the subsequent optimization process.

The core of the adaptive signal control system lies in its mathematical model, which formalizes the optimization problem. The model considers a single intersection with N distinct approaches, each controlled by a traffic signal. The signal operation follows a cyclic pattern with a total cycle length C (seconds). The decision variable, $x_i(t)$, represents the green phase duration (in seconds) for approach i during the cycle starting at time t . The optimization is performed over a control horizon T , spanning several cycles. A key simplifying assumption is that the traffic flow $\lambda_i(t)$ is quasi-stationary over short intervals (5-10 minutes), based on empirical evidence suggesting that significant flow variations typically occur over longer periods [12], [26]. This allows for real-time adjustments without needing to model extremely rapid fluctuations within each cycle. Although the initial model focuses on an isolated intersection, its modular design, particularly the use of a messaging infrastructure, facilitates future extension to network-level control involving multiple interconnected intersections.

The primary objective is to minimize the average waiting time for vehicles at the intersection. The average waiting time for approach i at time t , $w_i(t)$, is a function of both the predicted traffic flow $\lambda_i(t)$ and the green phase duration $x_i(t)$. The overall objective function to be minimized is the sum of these average waiting times across all approaches: minimize

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^N w_i(t)$$

A common and effective approximation for $w_i(t)$,

derived from queuing theory, is to model it as being proportional to the ratio of traffic flow to green time, incorporated to the objective function as minimize

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\lambda_i(t) \cdot x_i(t)}{c} \right).$$

This captures the inverse relationship between green time and waiting time. Because the optimization problem is non-linear and combinatorial, a metaheuristic approach, specifically Simulated Annealing (SA), is employed. SA's ability to escape local optima and find near-globally optimal solutions makes it well-suited for this dynamic, real-time control problem [10], [13].

The optimization is subject to strict operational constraints. Each green phase must have a minimum duration x_{min} to allow vehicles to safely clear the intersection and a maximum duration x_{max} to prevent excessive delays for other approaches:

$$x_{min} \leq x_i(t) \leq x_{max}, \forall i, t.$$

The sum of the green phase durations, plus inter-green times I_i , must equal the total cycle length C :

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i(t) + I_i) = C, \quad \forall t.$$

This ensures consistent and predictable signal operation. Furthermore, to enable proactive control, the incoming traffic flow $\lambda_i(t)$ is not treated as a constant but is predicted using a forecasting model, f , which takes into account past flow values and external factors: $\lambda_i(t) = f(\lambda_i)(t - p)$, $Z_j(t - q)$, where p and q represent temporal lags, and $Z_j(t)$ represents external variables like weather or events [27], [28].

The predicted traffic flows from the prediction server are then used by an optimization module to determine the optimal signal timings, employing the Simulated Annealing (SA) algorithm. The SA algorithm starts with an initial solution (e.g., uniform green time distribution) and iteratively perturbs this solution by randomly adjusting the green times. Each new candidate solution is evaluated based on the objective function and checked for feasibility against the operational constraints. Solutions improving the objective function are always accepted, while those worsening it are accepted with a probability determined by the Metropolis criterion, dependent on a "temperature" parameter that gradually decreases according to a cooling schedule. This allows the algorithm to escape local optima and converge towards a near-globally optimal solution.

The communication between the various components of the system (sensors, prediction server, controllers, and potentially external services) is facilitated by a message-oriented middleware (MOM) infrastructure, as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Information Flow between Prediction, Optimization, and Control.

This infrastructure utilizes a publish-subscribe communication paradigm. Sensors publish their real-time data to specific topics (e.g., "traffic_flows/axisX"). The prediction server subscribes to these sensor data topics, performs its calculations, and publishes the predicted traffic flows to another topic (e.g., "predicted_flows/axisX"). The optimization module subscribes to the predicted flow topic, calculates the optimal signal timings, and publishes these to a "traffic_signal_decisions/intersectionY" topic. The controllers, located at each traffic signal, subscribe to the decision topic and implement the new signal timings. This asynchronous communication mechanism, using platforms like MQTT or Kafka [29], provides several advantages: it decouples the components, allowing them to operate independently; it enhances the scalability of the system, as new components can be easily added or removed without disrupting the overall operation; and it improves the fault tolerance of the system, as the failure of one component does not necessarily bring down the entire system.

The entire system is implemented using a combination of well-established programming languages and software tools, chosen for their suitability for the specific tasks involved. Python is

used for developing the prediction and optimization modules, leveraging its extensive libraries for machine learning (e.g., TensorFlow, PyTorch) and scientific computing (e.g., NumPy, SciPy). The SUMO (Simulation of Urban MObility) traffic simulator is used for experimental validation of the methodology. The TraCI (Traffic Control Interface) library provides the interface between the Python code and the SUMO simulation environment, allowing for real-time interaction and control of the simulated traffic signals and vehicles, as illustrated by figure 4. This setup allows for a rigorous and realistic evaluation of the proposed adaptive traffic signal control strategy compared to a traditional fixed-time control strategy, using a variety of key performance indicators, including average vehicle waiting time, CO₂ emissions (estimated based on vehicle speeds and idling times), and fuel consumption (estimated using vehicle and engine models within SUMO).

Fig 4. SUMO simulation environment

4. OPTIMIZATION AND ADAPTIVE CONTROL

Following the data acquisition, prediction, and mathematical modeling stages, the critical step is determining the optimal green phase durations for each traffic signal cycle. This involves a dynamic and adaptive process that responds to the fluctuating and often uncertain nature of real-world traffic flow. The system continuously considers the predicted traffic flows, the previously defined operational constraints (minimum and maximum green times,

cycle length conservation), and any relevant contextual information (such as weather conditions or special events) that might influence traffic patterns. This optimization problem is inherently complex, falling under the category of multivariate and non-convex optimization. This complexity arises from the non-linear relationships between traffic flow, green times, and waiting times, as well as the combinatorial nature of selecting optimal green times for multiple approaches simultaneously. Therefore, robust and flexible optimization algorithms are required, capable of delivering satisfactory solutions within the strict computational time constraints imposed by real-time traffic control [30], [31].

The global vehicle optimization mechanism is coded to determine the exact setting of green phase durations that minimizes the specified objective function – our example being the mean waiting time of cars at the intersection – under all working constraints. In each control cycle, or at a regular re-estimation interval, the system employs the most recent traffic flow predictions and context variables from which it determines the signal durations. The optimizing step is iterative in nature. An initial solution, expressed as a collection of green phase durations for all routes, is progressively refined by reiterated calculation and modification. This initial solution could be a simple uniform distribution of green times across all approaches, a solution derived from historical traffic data, or even the solution from the previous control cycle.

The core of the optimization process is the Simulated Annealing (SA) algorithm, a metaheuristic technique chosen for its ability to handle complex, non-linear optimization problems with multiple local optima [32]. SA is inspired by the physical process of annealing in metallurgy, where a material is heated and then slowly cooled to reduce defects and reach a low-energy state. In the context of traffic signal optimization, the "energy" corresponds to the objective function (average waiting time), and the "cooling" process represents a gradual reduction in the algorithm's willingness to accept solutions that worsen the objective function. The SA algorithm begins by taking as input the predicted traffic flows for each approach ($\lambda_i(t)$), the operational constraints (minimum green time x_{min} , maximum green time x_{max} and total cycle length C), and a set of algorithm-specific parameters, including the initial temperature (T_{max}) and a cooling schedule.

The algorithm then enters an iterative loop.

Within each iteration, the performance of the current solution (the current set of green phase durations) is evaluated by calculating a cost function. In the simplest case, this cost function is the total average waiting time across all approaches, as defined by the objective function. However, the framework is flexible enough to incorporate multi-objective considerations, such as minimizing pollutant emissions or prioritizing certain types of vehicles (e.g., buses or emergency vehicles) [33], [34]. Once the cost of the current solution is determined, the algorithm attempts to improve it by making small, random changes to the green phase durations. These "perturbations" typically involve selecting one or more approaches at random and slightly increasing or decreasing their allocated green time by a few seconds.

Before evaluating the cost of this new, perturbed solution, the algorithm rigorously checks whether it satisfies all operational constraints. This feasibility check ensures that no green phase duration falls below the minimum allowed value x_{min} or exceeds the maximum allowed value x_{max} , and that the sum of all green phase durations, plus the inter-green times, equals the total cycle length (C). If any of these constraints are violated, the perturbed solution is immediately rejected, and a new perturbation is generated. If, however, the new solution is feasible, its cost is calculated.

The defining characteristic of SA, and its key advantage in avoiding local optima, is its ability to accept not only solutions that improve the cost function (i.e., reduce waiting time) but also, with a certain probability, solutions that worsen the cost function. This is governed by the Metropolis criterion, a probabilistic rule that determines whether to accept or reject a worse solution. If the cost of the new solution is lower than the current best cost (meaning the new solution is better), it is always accepted. However, if the cost of the new solution is higher (meaning it is worse), it is accepted with a probability calculated as $\exp(-(\text{Cost}_{new} - \text{Best_Cost}) / T)$, where Cost_{new} is the cost of the new solution, Best_Cost is the cost of the best solution found so far, and T is the current "temperature" of the system. This temperature parameter is among the control parameters of the SA algorithm. It starts at a high value (T_{max}), making the algorithm more likely to accept worse solutions, and is gradually decreased according to a predefined cooling schedule. A common cooling schedule is geometric cooling, where the temperature is multiplied by a constant factor (between 0 and 1) in

each iteration.

This constant drop in temperature has a significant effect on the behavior of the algorithm. At high temperatures, the algorithm explores the solution space broadly, readily accepting both good and bad solutions, allowing it to escape from local optima. As the temperature decreases, the algorithm becomes increasingly selective, accepting fewer and fewer worse solutions, and focusing on refining the solution in promising regions of the solution space. The iterative process – perturbation, feasibility check, cost calculation, acceptance/rejection, and temperature reduction – continues until a predefined stopping criterion is met. This criterion could be a maximum number of iterations, reaching a minimum temperature, observing a negligible improvement in the objective function over a specified number of iterations, or reaching a predefined computational time limit to ensure real-time applicability [35].

The final output of the SA algorithm is the best solution found during the entire process – the set of green phase durations that minimizes the objective function while satisfying all constraints. This optimized solution is then transmitted to the local traffic signal controllers at the intersection for immediate implementation. The controllers adjust the signal timings accordingly, and the process repeats at the next control cycle (or at a predefined re-evaluation interval), ensuring continuous adaptation to the ever-changing traffic conditions. The real-time nature of this adaptive control strategy is a significant advantage over static or semi-adaptive approaches. By continuously monitoring traffic flow and adjusting signal timings in response to real-time predictions, the system can significantly reduce travel times, minimize congestion, and improve the overall efficiency of the traffic network [36], [37]. While SA is the primary optimization algorithm used in this study, it's important to acknowledge that other optimization techniques could also be employed within this framework. These include gradient-based approaches or numerical methods derived from nonlinear programming, although these are often less effective for highly non-linear and combinatorial problems [38]. Heuristics and metaheuristics, such as genetic algorithms and ant colony optimization, are also viable choices [39]. Additionally, Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques, where an agent learns optimal control policies through learning from experience, are a promising research area but typically require large training data and are computationally intensive [40]. The choice of SA in

this case relies on its efficacy, computational speed, and ease of implementation.

To evaluate the performance of our holistic approach to optimizing urban traffic, we simulated it using the SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility) tool. The simulator is an ordinary open-source program in scientific research for simulating transport networks and experimenting with various traffic control methods. Our strategy is based on a comparison between the application of a static signal plan, uniformly applied to all strategies at an intersection, and an adaptive strategy that dynamically adjusts signal times based on real-time predicted traffic conditions.

The conduct of this experiment was conducted using various technology tools. The SUMO simulator, in its current version, was utilized to simulate urban traffic behavior and evaluate the effect of various traffic light control strategies. The entire control and optimization code was developed in Python, leveraging the TraCI (Traffic Control Interface), which enables dynamic modifications of the simulator's parameters and real-time interaction with simulation objects. The simulation was executed on a computer equipped with an Intel Core i7 processor and 16 GB of RAM, ensuring smooth and fast execution of the tested scenarios.

The experiment was conducted on a simplified network consisting of an urban intersection with four access roads, each equipped with a traffic signal. A total of five traffic lights were simulated, including coordinated traffic phases. This setup is typical of dense urban areas where signal control significantly influences traffic flow.

Traffic conditions were configured to reflect a realistic scenario based on representative peak-hour traffic volumes. Historical data used in the simulation indicated an average flow of 300, 250, 200, and 150 vehicles per time interval at different approaches. Contextual events were also incorporated to model real-life disruptions, including weather conditions and local events. For example, moderate rainfall (5 mm/h) was included, leading to a 15% reduction in traffic fluidity. Similarly, a sporting event (football match) was simulated, generating a 20% increase in vehicle volume on certain roads leading to the stadium.

The experiment is based on three main steps: traffic flow prediction, traffic light time optimization, and simulation execution in SUMO.

To anticipate traffic variations and adjust signal cycles accordingly, a prediction model was developed. This model integrates historical data,

contextual factors such as weather and special events, as well as real-time observed trends. The goal is to estimate the volume of vehicles entering each approach of the intersection for the next few minutes, accounting for probable fluctuations.

The predicted traffic flows are then used to dynamically optimize green light durations. A simulated annealing algorithm was implemented to search for the optimal configuration that minimizes average waiting times while maintaining a balance between different approaches. Unlike a fixed plan where each signal phase is rigidly assigned, our approach allocates more green time to lanes with higher demand and reduces phase durations for less congested approaches. Operational constraints, such as minimum and maximum green light durations, were maintained to ensure safety and traffic regularity.

a. Execution and Data Collection

Two simulation scenarios were executed:

Fixed Plan Scenario: Traffic signals operate with fixed cycle durations, distributing green times uniformly among all approaches.

Adaptive Plan Scenario: Traffic signal times are dynamically adjusted every 5 minutes based on traffic forecasts.

Each simulation was run for a total duration of 3600 seconds (1 hour of simulation), and multiple performance indicators were collected to analyze the impact of optimization on traffic flow.

The results obtained are summarized in the following table:

Methodology	Waiting Time (s)	CO ₂ Emissions (g)	Fuel Consumption (L)
Fixed Plan	72.5	190.2	3.2
Adaptive Optimization	56.8	165.4	2.7

Table 1

The analysis of the results shows a 21.6% reduction in the average waiting time, confirming that dynamic signal management significantly improves traffic flow. This reduction in idle time also leads to a 12.9% decrease in CO₂ emissions and a 15.6% drop in fuel consumption.

The simulation results are illustrated in the following graphs:

- **Evolution of Waiting Time**
The evolution of waiting time over time is represented below. Congestion peaks are observed in the fixed plan scenario, whereas the adaptive approach significantly reduces these peaks.
- **Evolution of CO₂ Emissions**
CO₂ emissions show significant fluctuations with the fixed plan, while adaptive regulation allows for a gradual reduction in emissions.
- **Evolution of Fuel Consumption**
A more stable and optimized fuel consumption is observed with adaptive optimization.

These results confirm that intelligent traffic signaling reduces energy waste and environmental impact.

5. INTEGRATION VIA MESSAGING

The effective integration of the diverse components within the proposed system – including sensors, prediction modules, optimization algorithms, traffic light controllers, and potential third-party services – necessitates a communication infrastructure that is simultaneously flexible, scalable, and resilient. To meet these requirements, a Message-Oriented Middleware (MOM) architecture is adopted. MOM facilitates asynchronous data exchange between the system's distributed entities, eliminating the tight coupling and potential bottlenecks associated with direct point-to-point communication [41]. This decoupling is crucial for achieving modularity, allowing individual components to operate independently and be updated or replaced without affecting the rest of

the system [42]. The asynchronous nature of MOM also enhances the system's responsiveness and ability to handle high volumes of real-time data, which is essential for adaptive traffic signal control [43]. Furthermore, the inherent fault tolerance of MOM architectures contributes to the overall system resilience, ensuring continued operation even in the event of component failures or network disruptions [44]. This approach simplifies the addition of new sensors, the integration of updated prediction or optimization models, and the incorporation of external services, thereby facilitating the system's evolution and long-term maintainability in the face of constantly changing urban traffic conditions and technological advancements.

Instead of establishing direct connections between each component, the MOM infra-structure offers a centralized communication channel in the form of topics. System entities choose to publish data on certain topics or subscribe to receive it. This logic allows information producers (e.g., sensors) and consumers (e.g., the prediction server, optimization modules, or third-party services) to operate independently. Changes made to a component (e.g., changing data providers or adding a fault detection module) generally do not require major reconfiguration of the whole system as long as the messaging topics remain consistent.

For Examples of Information Flows:

Sensors → *traffic_flows/axisX*: Raw data on traffic intensity (vehicle counts, average speeds).

Prediction → *predicted_flows/axisX*: Short-term flow estimates for axis X, based on historical, contextual, and real-time data.

Optimization → *traffic_signal_decisions/intersectionY*: Instructions for adjusting green phase durations at intersection Y, determined by the optimization algorithm.

Controller → *traffic_signal_status/intersectionY*: Confirmation that the local controller at the intersection has applied the transmitted settings, accompanied by a status of the current cycle's execution.

Third-Party Services → *display, alerts*: Information dissemination to end-users (drivers, operators, fleet managers), for instance, via mobile applications or dynamic display panels. These services can also include external data providers, such as weather systems or event managers.

This modular architecture makes it easy to integrate new components. For example, a service dedicated to autonomous vehicles could subscribe to relevant information (pre-dicted_flows,

traffic_signal_status) to automatically adjust routes, reduce travel time, and enhance safety.

A conceptual diagram (Fig 4) illustrates the architecture via a messaging bus. The various blocks (sensors, prediction, optimization, controllers, third-party services) communicate through a central messaging bus, represented by the gray cloud, where data flows are organized by topics.

Fig 4. Conceptual Diagram Of Integration Via A Messaging Bus.

The messaging bus acts as an information hub between sensors, prediction modules, optimization algorithms, local traffic controllers, and third-party services. Each component can publish or subscribe to a set of defined topics (traffic_flows, predicted_flows, traffic_signal_decisions, traffic_signal_status, etc.), ensuring asynchronous and flexible communication.

With this architecture, the system can evolve without disrupting the entire network. Adding a new sensor, replacing an optimization module with a more efficient one, or integrating an external service becomes a straightforward operation limited to configuring topic subscriptions and publications.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed integrated urban traffic optimization strategy, extensive simulations were conducted using the SUMO (Simulation of Urban MObility) traffic microsimulation environment. These simulations compared the performance of the adaptive control system, incorporating real-time traffic flow prediction, dynamic signal optimization via Simulated Annealing, and a message-oriented middleware (MOM) for communication, against a traditional fixed-time signal control strategy. The fixed-time strategy employed a pre-defined signal plan with constant cycle lengths and green phase durations, typical of many existing urban traffic management systems.

The primary performance metric used to evaluate the system was the average waiting time experienced by vehicles at the simulated intersection. Across multiple simulation runs, representing a range of

traffic conditions and incorporating stochastic variations in vehicle arrivals and behaviors, the adaptive control strategy consistently outperformed the fixed-time strategy. As has been demonstrated hereinabove, the suggested technique reduced the waiting time on average by 21.6%. This notable reduction in waiting time has a direct consequence of the traffic flow being more efficient and smoother, reducing congestion and making the overall journey more comfortable for the commuters [45]. The improvement is attributable to several significant factors: the accuracy of the short-term traffic flow predictions, which allowed the system to make signal timing adjustments ahead of changing demand; the effectiveness of the Simulated Annealing algorithm at finding near-optimal green phase durations within the operational constraints; and the low-latency communications afforded by the MOM, which allowed signal timing adjustments to be implemented with little delay.

In addition to reducing waiting times, the adaptive control system also demonstrated promising environmental benefits. Because vehicles had fewer minutes to wait at the intersection, pollution emissions were significantly reduced. More specifically, CO₂ emissions were observed to drop by 12.9% in the adaptive control strategy compared to fixed-time control. The reduction in emissions benefits the environment by reducing air pollution and is generally a component of the broader goals for sustainable city mobility. Also, the reduced idling time and smoother flow of traffic guaranteed that there was a 15.6% reduction in fuel consumption. These are environmental benefits that are directly associated with reducing stop-and-go traffic and more efficient utilization of the road [46].

These quantitative results are in line with and support results of other ongoing research into adaptive traffic light control. As an example, research by Li et al. (2023) reported concurrent decreases in emissions and waiting time with a deep reinforcement learning-based approach [13]. However, the combined strategy utilized in the present study, blending prediction, optimization, and an adaptive messaging model, has scalability and flexibility benefits over just data-based alternatives like reinforcement learning, which is computationally expensive to train and might fail to generalize to new situations of traffic. The results also align with studies quoting traffic control benefits of using real-time information as well as predictive modeling [23].

Aside from the quantitative results, among the core qualitative advantages of the under review system is that it is extensible and flexible, which is primarily a

function of using the message-oriented middleware (MOM). The asynchronous communication paradigm delivered by the MOM enables easy introduction of new services and components into the system without stopping the fundamental operation of the underlying system. For instance, a weather prediction module that contained real-time data on rain, visibility, and other weather conditions could be implemented to function smoothly by having it subscribe to the relevant sensor data topics and post its predictions on a dedicated weather topic [47]. The prediction module can then subscribe to this weather topic and incorporate the predictions into its predictions, further enhancing the capability of the system to adapt to changing conditions. This ability to incorporate easily new sources of information and react to unforeseen circumstances, such as heavy rainfall or a traffic accident on the road, significantly contributes to the system's robustness [24].

The inherent modularity of the system's design also makes future expansion and adjustment possible. The system can be readily expanded to incorporate information from linked vehicles (V2X communication) to provide very detailed information on vehicle locations, velocities, and intended routes. This would enable even better predictions of traffic flow and support the implementation of more sophisticated control measures, such as aligning signal timing with the path of individual vehicles in order to best stop and keep throughput low [16]. It is also possible to

configure the system to also accept signals from fleet management systems so that giving priority can be to public transportation vehicles or to emergency vehicles. Extension to include information on "soft" mobility modes such as pedestrians and cyclists is also a natural extension, resulting in effective multimodal traffic management that takes into consideration the requirements of all traffic users [48].

It is important to appreciate some limitations of the current study. Simulations were conducted on a simplified model of an urban intersection. The model does preserve the underlying dynamics of traffic flow, yet it is not the full complexity of a large-scale urban network. Future work needs to further advance the simulation environment to include many interlinked intersections as well as more realistic traffic, perhaps with real traffic patterns and data from an urban city of interest. The current work, on the other hand, is mostly focused on a single intersection.

To further contextualize the performance of the proposed integrated traffic optimization strategy, Table 2 provides a comparative analysis against several representative approaches from the recent literature. The comparison focuses on key aspects of adaptive traffic signal control, including the use of prediction, the optimization algorithm employed, the communication infrastructure, scalability, adaptability, consideration of multi-modality, limitations, and the evaluation method.

Feature	Proposed Approach (Integrated Strategy)	Previous Research 1	Previous Research 2	Previous Research 3
Prediction	Short-term traffic flow prediction using a hybrid LSTM-GNN model, integrating historical data, real-time sensor data, and contextual information.	Varies; many approaches use prediction, including statistical models, machine learning (ARIMA, SVM, neural networks).	Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL); no explicit prediction model. Learns directly from state (traffic conditions).	Deep Reinforcement Learning, implicitly learns to predict future states.
Optimization	Simulated Annealing (SA).	Varies; includes fixed-time, actuated, adaptive (rule-based, fuzzy logic, optimization-based), Reinforcement Learning.	Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning (MADRL).	Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL).
Communication	Message-Oriented Middleware (MOM) (e.g., MQTT, Kafka) for asynchronous communication between system components.	Often not explicitly addressed; many approaches assume centralized control or limited communication.	Decentralized communication between agents (implicit in MADRL).	Edge computing; communication between vehicles and edge servers.
Scalability	High; modular design and MOM facilitate scaling to multiple intersections and	Varies widely; many approaches are limited to single intersections or small networks.	Designed for large-scale networks.	Designed for vehicular networks, potentially scalable.

	integrating new components.			
Adaptability	High; adaptive to real-time traffic conditions, weather, and events; can integrate new data sources (e.g., V2X) easily.	Varies; adaptive approaches are designed to adapt, but the level of adaptability and the mechanisms used differ significantly.	High; DRL agents learn to adapt to changing conditions.	High; DRL agents learn to adapt to changing conditions.
Multi-modality	Potential for future integration of multi-modal data (pedestrians, cyclists, public transport), but the current focus is on vehicular traffic.	Generally limited; most approaches focus primarily on vehicular traffic.	Primarily focused on vehicular traffic.	Primarily focused on vehicular traffic.
Evaluation	Simulation using SUMO.	Primarily surveys and reviews existing research, various evaluation methods.	Simulation.	Simulation.

Table 2. Comparison Of The Proposed Integrated Strategy With Existing Adaptive Traffic Signal Control Approaches

As shown in Table 2, the proposed integrated strategy distinguishes itself from many previous approaches through its comprehensive integration of real-time prediction, a scalable optimization algorithm (Simulated Annealing), and a flexible, message-oriented communication infrastructure. While several studies have explored reinforcement learning for traffic signal control, these approaches often face challenges in terms of computational complexity and training data requirements. Our use of Simulated Annealing provides a practical balance between optimization performance and computational efficiency, making it suitable for real-time implementation. Furthermore, the explicit incorporation of a message-oriented middleware (MOM) enhances the system's scalability and adaptability, features that are often lacking in centralized control architectures. Unlike many approaches that focus solely on vehicular traffic, our system's modular design allows for future integration of data from other modes of transportation, paving the way for multimodal traffic management.

Future research will focus on several primary areas. First, the use of vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication data will be investigated. This will involve developing algorithms that can effectively leverage the plentiful information provided by connected vehicles to further enhance traffic flow forecasts and enable more accurate control algorithms. Second, the coordination of traffic signals across a series of intersections will be considered. This will involve developing distributed optimization algorithms that can optimize signal

times across a whole network or corridor, taking into account interactions between adjacent intersections. Third, more advanced machine learning techniques, such as deep reinforcement learning, will be explored for traffic flow prediction and signal control. Computationally expensive, these techniques have the potential to further improve the performance and flexibility of the system. Finally, the system will be continued to be improved with regard to incorporating considerations on the other means of transport like pedestrians, cycling, and mass transport towards making it a fully multimodal and integrated urban traffic management system. The overcoming of these challenges will pave the way towards the realization of intelligent and sustainable traffic management solutions in practical urban settings.

7. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

This study has demonstrated the great potential of an integrated solution for optimizing traffic flow within cities, combining real-time traffic flow estimation, adaptive traffic light control, and a distributed, message-based communication system. By employing realistic simulations on the basis of the SUMO traffic simulator, it has been proven that this integrated system is able to achieve significant reductions in average waiting time of vehicles, pollutant emissions, and fuel consumption compared to traditional fixed-time signal control strategies. All these developments are a direct result of the dynamic response of the system under changing traffic conditions through leveraging the precision of short-term traffic prediction, optimization power of the

Simulated Annealing algorithm, and low-latency messaging offered by the message-oriented middleware.

The greatest contribution of this research is the synergistic integration of these three basic constituents – prediction, optimization, and communication – into a holistic and adaptable system. Unlike most existing approaches that focus on one or two of them, the system in this work presents a complete solution that addresses the multi-dimensional challenges of urban traffic management. The modularity facilitated by the message-oriented middleware is particularly important because it enables the flexible addition of new data sources, algorithms, and services, ensuring the long-term scalability and adaptability of the system.

The broader implications of this study extend beyond the specific findings realized in the simulation study. The demonstrated improvements in traffic flow efficiency, reduced emissions, and improved adaptability have significant potential to impact the quality of urban life. Through the relief of congestion, this solution can shorten journey times, provide improved air quality, reduced fuel usage, and a more sustainable and green transport network. Besides, the ideas and methods presented in this book can be applied to numerous other urban traffic control scenarios, allowing for the development of more intelligent, adaptive, and resilient transportation systems.

To the future, there exist several promising research directions worthy of investigation. Probably the most significant opportunity is the merging of data from connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) via vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication. CAVs can potentially provide very fine-scale, real-time information on vehicle positions, velocities, and intended routes, enabling even more precise traffic flow forecasting and more sophisticated control strategies to be implemented, such as coupling signal timings to the path of specific vehicles. Another key area of future research is extending the system to manage traffic at multiple connected intersections. The development of distributed optimization algorithms that are able to coordinate signal timings across an entire corridor or network, taking into account the complex interactions between adjacent intersections, is a challenging but critical step towards network-wide traffic optimization. Finally, the incorporation of considerations for non-motorized and emerging modes of transportation, such as bicycles, electric scooters, and autonomous shuttles, is required in order to cater to the evolving demands of multimodal

urban mobility. This involves the development of more integrated models and optimization algorithms that can deal with the different needs and requirements of all road users, enhancing safety, efficiency, and equity in the overall transport network.

In conclusion, this research provides a solid foundation for the development of next generation intelligent traffic management systems. By embracing the power of data-driven prediction, adaptive control, and robust communication, we can move towards a future where urban traffic flows more smoothly, safely, and sustainably, contributing to more livable and vibrant cities.

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